

An Extensible General-Purpose Data Gathering and Classification Platform: Maestro v2023

Assessment Session – User Guide, v1.2a, 2023/October

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What is Maestro?

Maestro v2023 is a digital platform that gathers data from the web (social networks, web pages, APIs, etc.), transforms, extends, and classifies that data (usually through machine learning algorithms). The resulting dataset can afterwards be consulted in the Maestro platform and downloaded or sent to external services.

Maestro currently supports data types like images, sounds, and text. Both general text data types (i.e., plain text) and specialized text data types (e.g., news articles and scientific papers) are available. Since Maestro has been designed with flexibility and extensibility, it allows for a wide array of use cases that involve data gathering, classifying, and performing other machine learning operations.

Goal: This user assessment session aims to evaluate Maestro v2023 by users with a “researcher” profile. This evaluation will be performed by developing a simple “Literature Review Automation” experiment. The gathered results will assess Maestro’s usability level and determine its future enhancements. The experiment is described below.

More information: António Miguel Martins, Alberto Rodrigues da Silva, Jacinto Estima. Streamlining Literature Reviews Using an Automatic and Flexible Data Gathering and Classification Platform. 31st International Conference on Information Systems Development (ISD2023), AIS.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1UtvS9VHY094_ilzJG0RnyBh8gl_4AgnE/view?usp=sharing

Conditions:

This user assessment session shall be conducted under the following conditions:

- All the tasks should be performed without further support or help.
- Use a computer with a reliable Internet connection and a modern browser (Google Chrome version 10+, Mozilla Firefox version 31+, Internet Explorer version 10+, Microsoft Edge version 18+, or Safari version 10+).
- The session is expected to last between 15 to 30 minutes.

Instructions:

1. Access <https://maestroai.pt>
2. Create a new user account and confirm your email.
3. Take a moment to explore Maestro's menus.
4. Create a new Search Context with a name of your choice.
5. Configure the Search Context to search for scientific papers related to automating literature reviews.
 - 5.1. Use the search string "*(automatic \$OR semi-automatic) \$AND literature review \$AND (system \$OR program)*" without the quotes ("").
 - 5.2. Select "Scientific Paper" from the "Data Type" field.
 - 5.3. Do NOT set it to iterate.
6. Advanced configurations:
 - 6.1. On the **fetch** tab:
 - Upload [this zip file \(https://drive.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/download/1414448696376725\)](https://drive.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/download/1414448696376725) as the initial datastream.
 - Set the maximum results to 5.
 - Set the fetchers to "ArXiv Fetcher" and "Google Scholar Fetcher".
 - Make sure the "yield after gathering data" option is selected.
 - Do not forget to save these settings by pressing the save button.
 - 6.2. On the **classify** tab:
 - Select the classifiers "Keyword Extractor" and "Paper Summarizer".
 - Do not forget to save these settings.
 - 6.3. On the **filter** tab:
 - Make sure the "Duplicate filter" option is selected.
 - 6.4. On the **analyze** tab:
 - Select the analyzers "Source Analyzer" and "Citations Analyzer".
 - Do not forget to save these settings.
 - 6.5. Leave all other advanced configurations as default.
7. Review the configurations.
8. Start the Search Context execution by pressing the "Start" button.
 - 8.1. You can monitor its execution by pressing the "Monitor" button.
9. When the execution reaches the "Review" stage:
 - 9.1. Review the collected papers: if you think a paper seems unrelated to the search string, unselect it and click the "Save Changes" button. This option will remove it from the list of collected objects.
 - 9.2. Complete the review by clicking the "Complete review" button when you are done.
10. Monitor the progress and wait until all stages are finished.
 - **Note:** The "Classification" stage may take some time to complete. We recommend you leave it running in the background during this period. Furthermore, some data objects might not contain a result for a given plugin. This situation is expected and should only be concerning if the "Classification" stage fails.
11. When finished, check the classification results by clicking on the "Results" button on the Search

Context details menu.

12. Download the results; you will be asked to submit this generated file later in the feedback form. This should include the data, metadata, results, and docx file.
13. Return to the Search Context details menu and press the “Analysis” button to view the generated charts using the selected plugins.
14. Congratulations! You have succeeded in creating and executing your first Maestro Search Context!

Please fill out the form below:

<https://forms.gle/cNwPD7k3Mf65SpsT9>

Thank you for your participation!